

Σ LUCIDATE

Workshop report October 2024

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Executive Summary

- Modelling livestock disease outbreaks plays a critical role in modern epidemic preparedness.
- The strong links between policy, farmers, vets and researchers are extremely valuable and valued.
- Mutual respect, honesty, and communication are key within science and at the science policy interface.
- Animal traceability and surveillance in the UK is good, and modellers are finding it easier to access data as relationships build, but there is still some concern around data accessibility and the way it is used.
- There is a lot of work going into preparation for disease incursions, and outbreak response is well-rehearsed, though there may not be the capacity to deliver if there is more than one outbreak at a time.
- Decisions made based on models can have far reaching consequences for livelihoods, the wellbeing of humans and animals, and the environment.
- Values and choices embedded within models can be explored to make modelling more transparent.
- There need to be better ways of communicating how models work to non-modellers to make modelling more transparent and facilitate open decision-making processes.
- Models need to focus on a specific goal, such as rapid eradication or minimising cost. This must be considered in the context of all stakeholders' requirements and challenges and should be respectful of others lived experiences while still working in the public interest.

Introduction to ELUCIDATE

The enormous impact of livestock disease outbreaks on both animals and humans makes them a key one health challenge. A rapid, effective and well-planned response to such epidemics is a priority for governments. This workshop was designed to contribute to this effort by exploring the critical role that modelling plays in modern epidemic preparedness, and how this can be made clearer, more effective and more transparent across the modelling community, end users of modelling outputs, and groups impacted by disease outbreaks.

The workshop was funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), and facilitated by Dialogue Matters: experts in stakeholder participation, process design and facilitation: <https://dialoguematters.co.uk/>

It brought together 15 project participants, and 11 stakeholders, representatives of the modelling, science/policy brokerage, policymaking and farming communities as well as third sector organisations, (Appendix 1) to explore views on model development and use. As part of the ELUCIDATE project's responsible research and innovation framework the workshop aimed to ensure those affected by decisions on animal disease policy could assist in developing research approaches

The workshop plan, which was reviewed by The James Hutton Institute Research Ethics Committee, was designed to enable and encourage participants to share knowledge and ideas openly and freely by working through a series of participatory exercises, which included facilitated discussions and self-writing comments.

Data was collected through note taking at the workshop. These notes were then digitised and analysed thematically. The extensive amount of data collected has been condensed to highlight common themes for this report and the responses below represent many of the views participants expressed during the workshops. We have attempted to present a plurality of views rather than produce a single narrative about the workshop participants' perspectives. Information in quotation marks is taken verbatim from the notes made during the workshop.

The workshop began with the opportunity for participants to consider how the success of modelling in response to a disease outbreak could look in the future, before returning to the present and exploring the current situation.

Vision Question

Imagine it is 2030 and you are at an event celebrating the success of the use of modelling work in the response to an animal disease outbreak. The two things that please you most are...?

Participants thought that policy, researchers and stakeholders are working together effectively in 2030, accessing broad and inclusive evidence. They think that models are more accurate, useful and easily understood and that there are better decisions resulting from the models, which offer useful insights for policy makers (despite not perfectly predicting the future), so the impacts of outbreaks are minimised.

In addition, the transparent and open relationships between modellers, policy makers and researchers result in better mutual understanding, increased engagement and stronger collaboration to produce refined, accurate and dynamic models used to influence control measures before and during disease outbreaks. Model predictions, as part of the evidence base, lead to informed effective disease control decisions that are transparent, feasible and minimise financial detriment to the livestock industry. Full animal traceability and tools to anticipate and survey disease outbreaks has resulted in fewer serious outbreaks which leads to effective and timely disease control and minimal culling of animals, thus protecting commercial and rare breeds. Where necessary there is financial and emotional support for keepers and businesses affected by controls.

Someone commented that they would like to see "a reduction in the number of animals being farmed and that policy is in place to support a diet shift and frame practices that restore ecosystems, including crop/animal mixes and forestry, and protect workers rights"

The wider context for discussion

Participants were asked to consider what trends and changes are taking place now, that need to be considered when thinking about modelling animal disease outbreaks. Their comments were broken down into political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental headings and are summarised below.

Political

Participants felt that Brexit has resulted in uncertainty in the British livestock sector. There are issues with importing livestock from Europe (long journey times and the cost of health certificates) and concern that imported food may not have the same high animal welfare standards as the UK, which results in higher prices for home grown produce.

There was a concern around the impacts of potential Scottish devolution and the potential impacts on funding and data sharing. There was also concern that expert input may not fit the future political agenda, resulting in fewer jobs in the research industry. Despite a perceived need for the devolved nations to work together, participants voiced concern about the uncertainty of changing priorities and the political agenda of different governments.

Changes in subsidies for agriculture are leading to uncertainty in the sector. In addition, the unpredictability of international trade and civil unrest in many countries is a concern for global collaboration and data sharing opportunities.

Participants felt that there is a growing tension between urban and rural populations which may increase as farmers (who are in the minority of voters) are increasingly mandated to follow agendas that they fear may be detrimental to the livestock industry and their livelihood.

Economic

Increasing financial burdens on the government are resulting in less money in the public sector leading to some actual or potential reductions in financial support for farmers. Many farmers have insufficient resources (labour/financial) to carry out the necessary biosecurity measures related to disease control and to bear the costs of business interruption during a disease outbreak. While some participants felt that stringent biosecurity practices should be considered an investment, others thought that without financial support this may not always be feasible. The cost-of-living crisis is leading to the desire for cheaper food and the increase in fewer, larger farming businesses. This change may conflict with the requirement for more sustainable farming practises.

It was highlighted that Britain's livestock has a high health status in comparison to many other countries and that protecting this status drives imports and disease control measures.

Social

Participants perceived a distrust of farmers, science and 'experts', fed by fake news and conspiracy theories, often widely circulated on social media. Participants also stated that public perceptions of livestock farming are changing. While the ethical acceptability of livestock production and consumption is being questioned by some people, others felt that the increasing human population requires increased protein of animal origin.

There are likely to be fewer, larger farming businesses in future as the sector continues to consolidate, and smaller farms are lost. Farmers' mental health is already a concern, and this concern may increase with further regulatory pressure. Participants felt that the stigma of a farm contracting a notifiable disease and its effect on a business could add to that pressure. The increasing value of the farming landscape, social and financial and open access to the public, brings added pressure and, in some cases, conflict between farmers and the public.

Technology

There are increasing demands on farmers to produce, store, make use of and share data about all aspects of farming and animal production to comply with legal requirements or best practice recommendations. However, there may be no financial support to cover the costs of these requirements, laying further financial pressure on the farmer. Added to this,

many rural areas have poor connectivity, restricting the efficacy of technology and increasing the stress on farmers trying to comply. It was noted that good connectivity does not always equal effective communication between the relevant parties (e.g. farmers and policy)

Participants suggested that modelling technologies do not work alone and that there is a need to develop ways of noticing 'how' technologies work and are used locally. Real time monitoring of the farming industry results in a massive increase in data. While advances in computing power can lead to increases in data collection and dissemination, and remote data collection, this offers both opportunities and risks.

Legal

To produce efficient and effective models, researchers commented on the need for timely access to data. At present there are barriers to this. Data access requirements and GDPR create barriers to the use of farm data. There is a need to develop well-defined ethics for modelling and increase the resources required to manage data access and security.

Participants thought that legislation for livestock keepers should be clear and simple, allowing farmers to understand and comply with the regulations. At present producers are subjected to inequalities in the standards of production, especially regarding imported goods.

It was suggested that there is neo-liberal¹ tendency to 'share responsibility' for farm animal health and welfare issues. 'Multispecies justice' and 'planetary justice' was also highlighted in relation to rights of non-human animals and the need to safeguard environmental sustainability.

Environmental

Participants were concerned that the unpredictability of climate change impacts are resulting in an increase in more/new disease vectors reaching the UK, resulting in more/new vector borne diseases and changes in the distribution of pathogens and parasites. In addition, the need for food production and food security, urban growth, wildlife refuges and loss of biodiversity from a limited landscape is a growing tension. Furthermore, encroachment into wildlife refuges, and rewilding, could lead to emerging diseases.

Given the environmental concerns stated, participants suggested that a One Health approach² to modelling is required, along with access to sources of environmental data.

Who is already doing what around modelling animal health and disease risk?

Who?	What?
Academics: including Vet epidemiologist Physicians Bioinformaticians Programmers Social Scientists	Academics work with theory and produce 'number based' models Qualitative approaches Risk assessment

¹ favouring policies that promote free-market capitalism, deregulation, and reduction in government spending:

² The One Health approach recognizes that the health of animals, people, plants, and the environment are linked, and that all those involved in protecting animal, human, and environmental health must work together to achieve the best health outcomes.

Historians Data providers /empirical collection Ethicists Historians Economists	
Policy Scottish Government Defra	Are involved with the interpretation of model output to policy input and questioning/challenging to improve modelling outputs and interpretation
Policy / farmers	Working to improve traceability, which although good in Scotland, may be less so elsewhere. There are concerns around cross border and import issues.
Government Agencies (e.g. APHA)	Involved in fundamental modelling work, interpretation and use of models
Breed societies	Active in the promotion of vaccination schemes, breeding of resistant lines and overseeing society sales and accreditation schemes for EAE (enzootic abortion in ewes)/MV (Maedi Visna)

What are the benefits of modelling animal diseases and outbreaks?

For policy

Participants suggested that to make informed decisions and produce clear, well-defined evidence-based legislation, policy makers need strong, coherent evidence, based on science, which identifies certainty and uncertainty and informs comparisons of different disease control options. The opportunity to use models to investigate different scenarios and identify potential detrimental impacts ahead of a disease incursion is an asset to effective disease control.

For researchers in general

Working with models and modellers, offers a lens to investigate relationships of power in relation to how science and policy interact. Research that directly informs policy decisions enables researchers to have a real-world impact and anticipate answers to questions before they are required. Working with farmers and stakeholders offers a greater understanding of the challenges to the farming sector and enables researchers to gauge the practicality of research outcomes.

For modellers specifically

Modellers also value the opportunity to make a practical and meaningful difference to society. Their research informs decisions affecting livestock industries and enables judgements on response times, cost and length of disease incursions. In addition, modelling offers opportunities to challenge preconceptions and presumptions against reality and can result in a real-world impact.

Working with government and industry enables access to data, identifies data gaps and offers a chance to access and make use of, in a meaningful way, the increasing amounts of data being collected.

For farmers

Models can support good farm management, resulting in better health and welfare and added value to the farmer. They can lead to a quick response to a disease incursion, reducing disease spread and minimising the impact to livestock and keepers.

For animal health professionals

Models provide the ability to plan and make informed decisions, give informed advice and respond to supply/market demands considering budget restraints. By using models in 'peace' time, animal health professionals have the opportunity to train and prepare for, disease incursions.

Three Horizons

What is on its way out?

Participants thought that livestock farming could be declining. There is a growing trend towards vegetarianism and veganism. Current and new/emerging diseases could cause significant economic impact throughout a food chain relying on animal production. There are fewer visits by government (and farm) vets and there is a risk of losing touch with farmers. There was a concern that a reduction in funding for research and fewer centres of expertise would result in less evidence to inform policy.

What is coming into view but not yet arrived?

Participants could envisage the use of artificial intelligence becoming the norm leading to an 'explosion' of modelling capacity and capability and driving policy response. An increase in sources of standardised, ready to use and useful data e.g. electronic farm health data may lead to increased traceability of animals and food.

There was concern about an unsettled political environment and an increase in resources directed to global conflicts. New and emerging diseases, and antimicrobial resistance in both human and animal are seen to be on the horizon, with the possibility of another global pandemic.

Conversely, a rise of humanities and ethics and a recognition of all animals as sentient beings could result in new policies leading to a positive impact on animal welfare and a reduction in disease outbreaks.

What is on or just over the horizon? What might the wild cards be?

Participants surmised that there could be a shift in the public diet towards eating more plant-based protein and lab grown meat. Agroecology could become increasingly important, and meat could be never, or rarely consumed. Rewilding could change the priority of livestock keeping, and the tension between food production and protecting the environment could become increasingly polarised. There could be a growing trend in the One Health model to protect humans and the environment.

What are the emerging opportunities we could make the most of?

Participants thought that there are opportunities for more effective collaboration and cooperation between stakeholders through digital technologies and improved information

flow. By tapping into standardised surveillance opportunities and building in the powers / data sharing agreements that allow better access to data, there may be more sources of accessible data. Better computing resources can facilitate multiple model runs, exploring model and parameter uncertainty.

The use of social media can offer faster and more collective, disease spread prevention actions to be undertaken by farmers and livestock keepers.

There are opportunities to further link animal and human health planning and build contextualised care into considerations of animal health and welfare management in general and to gain a better understanding of the return on investment of biosecurity

Capturing connections between animal disease outbreaks and other things

Below are the results of an exercise to capture connections within modelling for animal disease outbreaks. Participants provided wide ranging, and as can be seen below, in some cases tongue in cheek, responses.

What does ‘model’ mean to you in this context?

Participants thought that a model is a conceptual framework that aims to represent as accurately as possible a real-life scenario and a representation of reality that can be used to investigate likely outcomes under different scenarios. It can provide a useful answer or insight about a real-life system and a representation of possible realities – mathematical or otherwise. Models can be used to help control disease spread and understand the response of the livestock industry to a disease incursion. Participants also commented that models are ‘a black box’, ‘a mystery’ ‘maths’ and ‘an idea but not reality’.

What does good management of an animal disease outbreak mean to you?

Participants stated that good management starts with prevention and ultimately the elimination of disease. Measures to achieve this should be rational with decisions clearly communicated and understood and feasibly implemented following dialogue with all stakeholders. Restrictions on farmers should be proportionate to disease risk, vaccines should be available, and farmers should be encouraged to follow more stringent biosecurity measures, backed up by funding where required. Animals should be considered actors or stakeholders in management considerations and conversations.

Thinking about animal disease outbreaks

What is already known about animal health and disease risk in general?

Participants suggested that production diseases and losses may be seen by some farmers and vets “as inevitable”. Vaccinations can be effective but there is hesitancy about their

use, possibly related to economics, and in the case of novel vaccines, uncertainty around efficacy and side effects.

Farmers don't think about a disease in isolation. There are multiple disease risks to consider on farm as well as the cost / benefit analysis around good biosecurity. Most farmers are aware of the link between resiliency to disease and better living conditions for their animals, but not all can maintain the required standards. Economics and a lack of farm labour, along with the reduction in large animal/farm vets, are an issue.

There is an awareness of some risks, while others are still unknown. Local, and global, risks are increased when animals are traded and moved. Risks are not limited to animal health, they include a human health aspect, both zoonotic risk and mental health aspects.

What is already working well around responses to animal disease outbreak in general?

There are strong links between policy, farmers, vets and researchers. Working in partnership like this is extremely valuable and valued. The work towards the eradication of BVD is a good example of this. The Scottish Government is paying for a lot of disease monitoring and modelling & supporting farmers to enroll in schemes for disease prevention & management though some refinements are required.

Animal traceability and surveillance in Scotland is good, though traceability is not so efficient across UK borders. Participants expressed a perception that official communications via email and social media notifying livestock keepers about outbreaks of disease such as bluetongue disease or avian influenza were positively perceived and had value for the recipients.

Modellers are finding it easier to access data as relationships build, but there is still some concern as described below. There is a lot of work going into preparing for disease incursions, and outbreak response is well-rehearsed, though there may not be the capacity to deliver if there is more than one outbreak at a time.

What challenges are there?

Regarding modelling, there are still issues around data sharing and GDPR. Farmers may be reticent about sharing their data. Some data that is held by government agencies is relevant to modelling disease outbreaks but is not shared with modellers. Participants queried the appropriateness of some data sharing laws. They highlighted that in modelling there are challenges around making the model outputs comprehensible and the accuracy of models intended to produce predictive outcomes. Currently only one disease can be tackled at a time, a move towards 'systems thinking and approaches' would be helpful.

Despite a rise in collaborative working, pressures on government funds can increase silo working instead of promoting working together. This is apparent when considering research on human and animal diseases and is apparent in the challenges around dealing with diseases that are unpredictable, exotic and rare. Horizon scanning is becoming more challenging and there is a need to remain adaptive and responsive to evolving situations.

It was suggested that a very big challenge is to understand the 'butterfly effect'. E.g. indoor farming is preferred by many large commercial pig and poultry businesses to reduce disease risk, but relying on feed resources coming from abroad to accommodate more intensive animal production can push land use change across the globe, leading to deforestation in favour of animal feed production. As mentioned previously, climate change and the pressure of multiple land use causes its own issues. Disease transfer to farmed animals from wildlife is a risk e.g. African swine fever in wild boar, bluetongue in deer. There may also be a public health challenge from companion animals e.g. backyard poultry, cats and dogs which have the potential to play a role in disease transmission in a livestock epidemic. It was suggested that "all hell would break loose if there was a vector in pets".

Social media can be an effective method of reaching people, but it doesn't necessarily discriminate between different sources of information. Some people are actively encouraging misinformation online which causes concern and lack of trust in authority.

What more needs to be done?

Participants consistently mentioned improving disease prevention. For example, shifting to a more pro-active approach and encouraging good biosecurity, highlighting that it is a good return on investment. They thought that farming needs to be more profitable so farmers can take the necessary steps to protect their livestock, and that animal health should be considered a public good. As markets are thought to be a hot bed for disease, reducing the number of markets would be helpful in reducing the spread of disease. However, as not all livestock breeding areas can finish livestock, there is a need to move animals around the country from holding to holding. Despite the requirement for further action, one participant stated that "a lot is being done, but it's not really recognised/it's looked down on – makes me sad".

Changing or improving ways of sharing knowledge and making communications relevant in specific contexts, e.g. small holdings on an island versus large holdings on the mainland, mixed versus single animal species, could improve education and awareness. There could be more recognition of farmers knowledge and traditional husbandry skills and a more open-minded attitude to different systems, e.g. regenerative farming and agroecology.

It was suggested that thinking in a more 'joined up' way about animal disease, climate change and biodiversity, and recognising the need for new ways of thinking, including the limits of crisis and response thinking, could be advantageous. There is a need for parsimonious models³, and modelling that can handle big data, however there may be a trade-off as it's not clear to non-modellers what assumptions are being made by modellers.

Transnational and global collaboration and collaboration in general is still lacking and could be improved.

Thinking about modelling

What is already known about modelling, in its widest context?

Participants highlighted that modelling is a speculative science. Models require real world knowledge and good data. Models are a tool to help people think clearly about a topic. They can be predictive or speculative and can be used for testing scenarios. There is a trade-off between detail and real-world verisimilitude (precision) in a model and its usefulness, particularly when there is little information about model parameters, though it is possible to find a balance.

It is sometimes hard to attune models to their local context/environment and one size does not fit all (applies to science more broadly). Models can tell a lot about the data available and building models can help identify what data is available and what can be influenced by small changes.

Models are popular with policy makers, but many people aren't aware of them, don't think about them or are ambivalent to them. However, Covid highlighted modelling to the public, and the public are more interested and aware of modelling. It was thought that the rise in citizen science may also contribute to this awareness.

Participants pointed out that models can be iterative and always evolving. They are complex and can be controversial, incur distrust and may have unintended consequences.

³ simple models with great explanatory and/or predictive power.

They can be massaged to seem like they are coming from science and can be seen as being authoritative because they are quantitative. They can appear “black boxy⁴” and require a particular expertise to interpret and communicate them. Although they are expensive and time consuming, they may be cheaper than running a field trial, though trials may be required to test the model.

What is already working well around modelling, in its widest context?

Models are recognised as an important part of the evidence-base that informs disease control decisions. The UK (and devolved) governments utilise and listen to models and there is a lot of empirical evidence that modelling assumptions are effective. In the context of animal health, there are good relationships in modelling groups and across government administrations.

Modelling methodologies are always being improved, with more approaches and innovations taken. There is increasing access to better funding, data and computing power to support modelling and modellers who have huge amounts of expertise and technical skills, are no longer having to work in isolation,

What challenges are there?

Participants pointed out that funding and the data required to keep models updated can be hard to get. Models cannot be generated very quickly and the challenge of developing models ahead of time is that the questions asked then may not be right later. For instance, changes in behaviour e.g. virus mutations, can reduce the effectiveness of the model. Models are inherently biased as decisions are made by humans so assumptions may not be accurate. In addition, there is conflict between simplicity & complexity. Complexity may be more realistic but less generalisable. Modellers can be conscious and paranoid about caveats which can become a barrier to the usability of a model, and they need to find a balance. As some people don't understand what models are for and what to do with them, modellers must be aware of their audience, communicate assumptions and uncertainties and manage expectations.

What more needs to be done?

Modellers said they should be able to include the relevant processes and exclude irrelevant ones and would like to be allowed to model (without the burden of other concerns e.g. trade, human health), while decision makers take responsibility for how models inform decision making (including ethics). It is essential that what feeds into models is the best veterinary and medical knowledge and that knowledge beyond pathogens to other aspects including environmental conditions are included.

Models are generally poor at predicting specific futures, although they may predict a range of possible futures, and can be used as a framework to promote discussion or address specific arguments. Modelling can limit discussion of other more radical futures, while at the same time enable discussion to achieve iterative process between modellers and users of output.

There needs to be better communication in general around modelling to manage expectations - to policy, industry and between researchers and animal practitioners.

⁴ Black box-

a usually complicated electronic device whose internal mechanism is usually hidden from or mysterious to the user

What do policymakers/ researchers/ farmers/ animal health practitioners need from animal disease outbreak models?

Policymakers

Policymakers need transparency, clarity and confidence in the information they are given. Models need to be timely and based on robust, traceable scientific evidence, relating to reality. Interpretations and the limitations of the model need to be understood, and public and industry perception needs to be considered when models are used in decision making.

Researchers

When researching for policy, researchers need clear guidance and communication about policy objectives and requirements. Sufficient funding, access to reliable and timely data, and software that is fit for purpose, is key.

Models need to be replicable and portable (passed on and well documented). There is a need for better sharing of models and making them useable and interpretable by other modellers. Interdisciplinary collaboration should be improved, e.g. researchers that are not modellers need modellers to listen to them and understand their expertise.

Farmers

Farmers may appreciate the opportunity to engage with modellers and understand models if they wish to. They look for respect for their roles, and clear advice that is relevant, practicable and financially viable. They are concerned about the ethical use of their data and would like transparency about how their data is used.

Animal health practitioners

Vets (and others), need to understand how model outputs can be translated and adapted for practical application e.g. different farming practices or species. They require a more detailed understanding of models and outputs to support their role as interpreters and communicators to industry and to modellers. More education about modelling in veterinary degrees would be beneficial.

Thinking about everything you have discussed so far today, what ideas do you have for research on modelling animal disease outbreaks that could build on existing good work and/or address things that still need to be done?

Participants thought that there needs to be better ways of communicating how models work to non-modellers to help them better understand how decisions in modelling are made. If models are more open, available and useable by other groups then there's a better chance of building holistic models. However, a more holistic approach may necessitate the identification of new stakeholders and establishing further relationships.

Data exists but sharing is still an issue and needs to be streamlined. Farmers are recording real time data which modellers “could do wonders” with. There is a role for modellers to go to farmers and understand how best to help them. Participants thought that there is a requirement for more research on people's perceptions & trust of models and a need to think more about capturing human behaviour, in particular the heterogeneity among farmers, by communicating with them individually, not just the “top dogs” E.g. farming unions.

It was suggested that instead of focussing purely on the economic impact of an animal disease outbreak, think of modelling the health of the ecosystem and biodiversity (e.g. wildlife, avian influenza and land use change) and how changing land use affects wildlife.

What expertise and skills can policymakers/researchers/farmers/animal health practitioners bring to modelling animal disease outbreaks?

Policymakers

Participants stated that policymakers should understand the legislation and rules that governs disease management. They should be able to articulate clear questions regarding the meaning of a specific model and the ethics of modelling. While providing guidance and information around the modelling animal disease outbreaks they should be looking for unbiased evidence.

Policymakers should provide appropriate funding and help facilitate access to data. They should be able to use their relationships with other nations and align with global health organizations such as the World Health Organisation (WHO) to inform their decisions and hold accountability for their policy decisions.

They should understand the bigger picture, be aware of a range of social/political acceptable options and have a good understanding of the risk appetite of decision makers. Stakeholders stated that policymakers could better understand farmers' needs and circumstances and factor this into their decision making. It is also their role to bring together different groups of people, by linking farmers, vets and modellers and facilitating dialogue between groups. They should be overseeing everything, have expertise on what is good for society, defining objectives and putting constraints on specific actions.

Researchers

Participants felt that researchers can provide a range of skills e.g. technical, data interpretation, data management, quantitative & qualitative skills, communication skills and complementary skills that farmers don't have. They can also bring expertise from their discipline including novel modelling approaches (such as data fitting), knowledge of causes and consequences of diseases and outbreaks, expertise in communicating model outputs (such as visualisation), and have the capacity to translate policy makers questions into quantitative models.

They also recognise other expertise and disciplines and have scientific and disease knowledge. They work in a variety of different contexts, are open to working with people from different disciplines, open minded about solutions and may have left field ideas. Overall, researchers have the capacity to react, particularly in an outbreak.

Farmers

Farmers have extensive knowledge of animals and animal management. They have practical experience of varied agricultural systems, insights into animal behaviour and are grounded in the real-world. They understand disease prevention, and the early warning signs of disease and the subsequent outcomes. They have knowledge of geographical and

climate implications and the financial implications of management decisions. They hold prior experience of interventions used in the past and understand the policy options that people will tend to comply with. Farmers have the ability to collaborate with and influence other farmers, e.g. through peer to peer learning and monitor farms.

Animal health practitioners

Vets (and other practitioners) can give trusted, respected advice and provide a connection between modelling/models and farmers. They have a breadth of experience, work across broad areas and have experience of past and current practices. A good overview of multiple farms in an area gives them the capacity to benchmark farms and recognise attitudes and compliances of farmers. Most vet practices have farmer groups enabling the transfer of information to different organisations. As many vet practices are now conglomerates, they can collect data more easily, though they may not be able to pass it on.

What ethics, values and principles should guide how we work together?

Participants highlighted that mutual respect, honesty, and communication are key. There is a need to focus on a common goal, understand other's contexts and challenges and be respectful of others lived experiences while continuing to work in the public interest. Risks and rewards should be balanced, and the unintended consequences that affect livelihoods, the wellbeing of humans and animals, and the environment should be considered.

There is a need for stakeholders to trust expertise and for modellers to use their expertise responsibly. Accepting that modelling isn't value neutral (biases etc) and is an imperfect science doesn't mean that the science is wrong.

Researchers' reflections

Summary of the report

- Understanding and responding to flows (e.g., of animals, disease, funding, collaboration) and barriers (e.g., national and international borders, lack of political interest/will, barriers to research collaboration, data access) are key themes throughout the report. As is the importance of developing strong relationships between different actor groups for sharing information, building trust, and collaborating.
- The question of evidence (and whether models can act as evidence) is apparent throughout. What is evidence? How is it understood and used? Questions then arise in the workshop outputs around the reliability and robustness of evidence.
- Often, but not always, modelling was conceptualised in the workshop outputs as part of a reactive approach. That is, models are used to inform the response to disease outbreaks, rather than prevent disease in the first place.
- There was often quite a normative understanding of models/modelling apparent in the workshop outputs. That is, modelling is inherently a good thing to do, and producing better models will result in producing more good. However, the problematic elements of modelling and models were apparent in certain discussions, including -
 - o There was a recognition that models are to some degree guesswork (informed by data) but nevertheless need to be presented to policymakers with confidence and as absolutes (to build trust/authority in the models and modellers).
 - o Challenges exist around the relationship between modellers and policymakers, and between modellers and their models (the objectiveness – or not – of the act of modelling).

- o The questions - What makes a model 'good'? And how are models evaluated?
- Areas of tension/contradiction that arose from the workshop outputs that may require further unpacking, or greater detail to fully explain. This can be in part explained by the mix of participants from different backgrounds and disciplines. These included –
 - o Discussion of both not enough data/access to data and discussions of examples of sufficient data. There were some mentions of too much data.
 - o There were conversations around both not enough collaboration and effective collaborative working around animal disease modelling.
 - o There was a desire to inform and educate via a top-down approach (e.g., on models, and the outputs of models), as well as a desire to be more participatory (e.g., bottom up) in model development with "other groups", integrating their knowledges into model development.
 - o Mentions of GDPR preventing sharing of information between actors, but also some mention of needing to better protect farmers' information.

Themes emergent throughout the report

- Improving models (e.g., the construction, use, and understanding), and improving the situation (i.e., less disease, fewer impacts of disease) comes together in the point "better decisions result from models". Quite a lot of the problems identified around animal agriculture are not about models or modelling disease. It is important to consider wider changes and challenges in the wider farming system, e.g., around resources, finances, labour, pressure and farmer wellbeing.
- Perceptions of models and their role included discussions of them as representations, but with a recognition that sometimes people expect them to give definitive answers and consider them to have failed if they prove inaccurate. Models therefore need to be viewed as a part of, not the whole picture.
- Questions around 'good modelling practice' – the development of an ethical framework of modelling occurred throughout the workshop. These included -
 - o The need to consider the unintended consequences of modelling/models, reflect on their practice and take accountability. The need to remember that farmers are human and modelling assumptions can have real-life impacts upon them.
 - o Be more participatory/interdisciplinary when modelling. This can aid in developing better inputs and outputs.
 - o The ethical collection and use of data.
 - o Considerations of how models and the outputs of models are communicated.
 - o The systems modelled are often complex and dynamic, how can models keep up with constantly changing reality?
- There are challenges associated with misinformation and an associated need for transparency and trust building -
 - o There is a need to inform decision makers, and for decision makers themselves to make more informed decisions. This includes challenges around the communication and interpretation of models and what they present, worries about misuse/misunderstanding, need for clarity. There may be a need to help non-experts understand models, their limitations, how to interpret them, what they can and cannot do.

- o There are lots of data and increasingly advanced technology is available, but challenges exist around how to ensure flows of information and effective communication between different actors and sectors.
- o questions about action/inaction in response to models. Why do (some) people not act?
- o need for recognition of heterogeneity among farmers and other animal-keepers.
- The consideration of politics, e.g., relative power of farmers, policymakers, consumers, supermarkets, etc. Political agendas and social preferences affect wider farming/food system and practices, which then affects disease prevention and response.

Next steps

During a second workshop in April 2025, research ideas developed in this workshop will contribute towards developing further research proposals to address the second stage of the UKRI call on tackling epidemic threats

Appendix 1. List of participant affiliations

Affiliation	Male	Female
APHA	1	
BIOSS	5	
Farmers	4	1
Goldsmiths University of London		1
James Hutton Institute		2
Third sector organisations	1	1
Scottish Government	1	1
University of Edinburgh	2	2
University of Glasgow	1	3

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